

Tracking Maneuvering Targets With Multiple, Intermittent Sensors

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Abstract

In many multisensor systems, the number of sensors and the type of sensors supporting a particular target track can vary with time due to the mobility, type, and resource limitations of the individual sensors. This variability in the configuration of the sensor system poses a significant problem when tracking maneuvering targets because of the uncertainty in the target motion model. When the sensor system is fixed, the uncertainty in the motion model is addressed in the design of the tracking algorithm by considering individual target trajectories. However, considering individual target trajectories in conjunction with every possible multisensor configuration is not practical. In this paper, the problem of tracking maneuvering targets with multiple intermittent sensors is illustrated through an example involving a single motion model example. The Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) algorithm is applied to this problem and simulation results are given.

1. Introduction

When the problem of tracking maneuvering targets with multiple sensors is considered in the literature, the number and type of sensors that support a given target track are usually fixed with respect to a given location of the target. However, in many multisensor systems, the number of sensors and the type of sensors supporting a particular target track can vary with time due to the mobility, type, and resource limitations of the individual sensors. This variability in the configuration of the sensor system poses a significant problem when tracking maneuvering targets because of the uncertainty in the target motion model. A Kalman filter is often employed to filter the position measurements for estimating the position, velocity, and acceleration of a target. The dynamics model commonly assumed for a target in track is given by

$$X_{k+1} = F_k X_k + G_k w_k \quad (1.1)$$

where $w_k \sim N(0, Q_k)$ is the process noise and F_k defines a linear constraint on the dynamics. The target state vector X_k contains the position, velocity, and acceleration of the target at time k , as well as other variables used to model the time-varying acceleration. The linear measurement model is given by

$$Y_k = H_k X_k + v_k \quad (1.2)$$

where Y_k is usually the target position measurement and $v_k \sim N(0, R_k)$ is the observation errors. Both w_k and v_k are assumed to be "white" noise processes that are independent.

When designing the Kalman filter, Q_k is selected as a constant Q such that the 70 to 95% confidence region about zero contains the maximum acceleration level of the target. However, when targets maneuver, the acceleration changes in a deterministic manner. Thus, the white noise assumption associated with w_k is violated and the filter will develop a bias in the state estimates. If a larger Q is chosen, the bias in the state estimates will be less during a maneuver, but the Q will characterize the target motion poorly when the target is not maneuvering and the filter performance will be far from optimal.

Case studies of a single sensor tracking algorithm have shown that additional data from a second sensor can degrade the quality of the target track [1]. When a multisensor system is fixed, the uncertainty in the motion model is addressed in the design of the tracking algorithm by considering individual target trajectories and selecting a Q that provides a reasonable performance over all trajectories. However, considering individual target trajectories in conjunction with every possible multisensor configuration is not practical when more than two sensors may be used for tracking. Furthermore, if the measurements are nonlinear in the target state, additional filter designs would be required for the different measurement regions of the sensors.

In order to address this problem of motion model uncertainty, the motion of the target will be represented by multiple models which are hypothesized to be correct. Such a linear system with Markovian switching coefficients can be represented as

$$X_{k+1} = F_k(\theta_{k+1})X_k + G_k(\theta_{k+1})w_k \quad (1.3)$$

with observations

$$Z_k = H_k(\theta_k)X_k + v_k \quad (1.4)$$

where θ_k is a finite state Markov chain taking values in $\{1, \dots, N\}$ according to the transition probability p_{ij} of switching from model i to model j . The optimal approach to estimating the state of the system in Eqs. (1.3) and (1.4) requires that every possible sequence of models from the initial observation through the most recent measurement be considered. Thus, for r models, the optimal approach requires r^k filters for processing the k^{th} observation. Since this optimal approach is not practical, efficient management of the multiple hypotheses is critical to limiting the computational requirements, while maintaining the performance capability of the algorithm. The Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) algorithm [2,3] is a novel approach to merging the different model hypotheses. In the IMM algorithm, the state estimate is computed under each possible model hypothesis for the most recent sampling period with each model using a different combination of previous model-conditioned estimates. The r hypotheses are then merged to compute the output state estimate and associated error covariance. Previous investigations documented in the literature indicate that the IMM algorithm is the superior technique when the computational requirements of the different techniques are considered [4,5]. In this paper, the problem of tracking maneuvering targets with multiple intermittent sensors is discussed and the IMM algorithm is applied to this problem.

This paper is organized as follows. A tracking example involving a constant velocity tracking filter is given in Section 2 to illustrate the problem of filter consistency associated with tracking maneuvering targets with multiple, intermittent sensors. The IMM algorithm is presented in Section 3. In Section 4, the IMM algorithm is applied to the tracking example of Section 2 as a potential solution to the problem of filter consistency. Concluding remarks are given in Section 5.

2. Illustrative example

The constant velocity Kalman filter will be used to illustrate the problem of filter consistency that occurs

when tracking maneuvering targets with multiple intermittent sensors. The constant velocity filter is based on the assumption that the target is moving with constant velocity plus zero-mean, white Gaussian acceleration errors that are piecewise constant. In order to simplify the example and permit analytical predictions of the filter performance, the motion of the target will be defined in a single coordinate and the measurements will be the positions of the target (i.e. a linear function of the state). For the constant velocity Kalman filter, the state and measurement equations of Eq. (1.1) and (1.2) are defined by

$$X_k = [x_k \quad \dot{x}_k]^T \quad (2.1)$$

$$F_k = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & T \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.2)$$

$$G_k = \begin{bmatrix} T^2 & T \\ 2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (2.3)$$

$$H_k = [1 \quad 0] \quad (2.4)$$

$R_k = \sigma_v^2$ in the variance of the measurements in m^2 , and $Q_k = \sigma_w^2$ in the variance of the acceleration errors in m^2/s^4 .

The steady-state form of the constant velocity filter will be used for analytical predictions of filter performance. For a constant velocity filter to achieve these steady-state conditions, the error processes, w_k and v_k , must be stationary and the data rate must be constant. The α, β filter is the steady-state Kalman filter for the constant velocity filter. For the α, β filter,

$$K_k = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \beta \\ & T \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (2.5)$$

where α, β gains are determined as in [5,6] by solving the simultaneous equations

$$\Gamma^2 = T^4 \frac{\sigma_w^2}{\sigma_v^2} = \frac{\beta^2}{(1-\alpha)} \quad (2.6)$$

$$\beta = 2(2-\alpha) - 4\sqrt{1-\alpha} \quad (2.7)$$

The $\Gamma = T^2 \frac{\sigma_w}{\sigma_v}$ known as the tracking index is often used to characterize the design of tracking filters. When the noise processes are not stationary or the data rate is not constant, the α, β gains will not agree exactly with the corresponding Kalman gains.

For analytical predictions of filter performance, the α, β filter is viewed as a linear, time-invariant system with an input that can be expressed as a deterministic signal plus white noise measurement errors. The input-output relationships between the measurements Y_k and

Fig. 1. Maximum average RMSE in state estimates

the state estimate $X_{k|k}$ can be expressed as a linear system that is given by

$$X_{k|k} = \bar{F}X_{k-1|k-1} + \bar{G}Y_k \quad (2.8)$$

where

$$\bar{F} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - \alpha & (1 - \alpha)T \\ -\frac{\beta}{T} & (1 - \beta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.9)$$

$$\bar{G} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \frac{\beta}{T} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (2.10)$$

Using Eq. (2.8) provides the error covariance of $X_{k|k}$ that results from the measurement errors as given in [6] to be

$$\bar{S}_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{\sigma_v^2}{\alpha d_1} \begin{bmatrix} 2\alpha^2 + \beta(2 - 3\alpha) & \frac{\beta}{T}(2\alpha - \beta) \\ \frac{\beta}{T}(2\alpha - \beta) & \frac{2\beta^2}{T^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.11)$$

where $d_1 = 4 - 2\alpha - \beta$. If a target trajectory is characterized by a constant acceleration denoted as A , then constant biases develop between the outputs of α, β filter and the true values of the elements of target state.

Fig. 2. RMSE in state estimates for example

Using Eq. (2.8) [6,7], the steady-state bias vector of the target state is given to be

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} (1 - \alpha)\frac{T^2}{\beta} & (\frac{\alpha}{\beta} - 0.5)T \end{bmatrix}^T A \quad (2.12)$$

The maximum average Root-Mean-Square Errors (RMSEs) in the position estimates of the α, β filter can be expressed as

$$\overline{\text{RMSE}}_p = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_v^2}{\alpha d_1} (2\alpha^2 + \beta(2 - 3\alpha)) + (1 - \alpha)^2 \frac{T^4}{\beta^2} A_{max}^2} \quad (2.13)$$

where A_{max} is the maximum expected acceleration of the target and d_1 is defined with Eq. (2.11). The maximum average RMSE in the velocity estimates can be expressed as

$$\overline{\text{RMSE}}_v = \sqrt{\frac{2\sigma_v^2\beta^2}{\alpha d_1 T^2} + (\frac{\alpha}{\beta} - 0.5)^2 T^2 A_{max}^2} \quad (2.14)$$

As an example, two tracking systems with a 1 Hz measurement rate will be considered for tracking ma-

neuvering targets that can achieve a maximum acceleration of 20 m/s^2 . The measurements of each sensor are corrupted with zero-mean errors that are Gaussian distributed and have a standard deviation of 25 m. Fig. 1 gives $\overline{\text{RMSE}}_p$ and $\overline{\text{RMSE}}_v$ versus the tracking index given in Eq. (2.6). The 1 Hz lines of Fig. 1 correspond to a single sensor track, while the 2 Hz lines correspond to a two sensor track where the measurement times of the two sensors are offset by 0.5 s.

The single sensor tracking filter is designed to have a tracking index of 0.5 which corresponds to point "A" on the 1 Hz lines. For this filter, $\overline{\text{RMSE}}_p$ and $\overline{\text{RMSE}}_v$ are 31 m and 32.5 m/s, respectively. If the second sensor also provides data to this filter, the tracking index becomes 0.125 which corresponds to point "B" on the 2 Hz lines. For the filter with data from both sensors, $\overline{\text{RMSE}}_p$ and $\overline{\text{RMSE}}_v$ are 34 m and 36 m/s, respectively. Thus, the addition of the data from the second sensor results in larger maximum average RMSEs in the filter outputs. For simulation studies of these analytical results, a target that maneuvers with a constant acceleration of 20 m/s^2 from 15 to 35 s was considered. Fig. 2 gives the results from a Monte Carlo simulation with 200 experiments for the filter operating at points "A" and "B." Fig. 2 shows the data from the second sensor reduces the RMSE when the target is not maneuvering. However, Fig. 2 also shows that the RMSE during the maneuver is increased by the addition of the data from the second sensor. If the point "C" of Fig. 1 is chosen as the design of the filter receiving data from both sensors, $\overline{\text{RMSE}}_p$ and $\overline{\text{RMSE}}_v$ are less than those of original filter designed to operate at point "A." Thus, the data from the second sensor improves the tracking if the filter design is changed to correspond to point "C" when both sensors are providing data. Simulation results for the filter designed to operate at "C" are given in Fig. 2. Note that the maximum average RMSEs in position and velocity are smallest for design C. However, design C provides the largest RMSE in velocity when the target is not maneuvering. The RMSE in position of design C is slightly smaller than that of design A when the target is not maneuvering.

Since this example involves only two sensors with measurements that are linear in the target state, a procedure could be designed to adapt the filter for the different sensor combinations. However, when many different sensors may provide data to the filter, the number of possible filter designs may be very large and selecting the appropriate design could be difficult. Furthermore, if the measurements are nonlinear in the target state, additional filter designs would be required for the different measurement regions.

Fig. 3. IMM algorithm

3. IMM algorithm

The IMM algorithm consists of a filter for each model, a model probability evaluator, an estimate mixer at the input of the filters, and an estimate combiner at the output of the filters. The flow diagram of an IMM algorithm with two models is given in Fig. 3, where $X_{k|k}$ is the state estimate based on both models, $X_{k|k}^j$ is the state estimate for time k based on model j , Λ_k is the vector of model likelihoods at time k , and μ_k is the vector of model probabilities at time k when all the likelihoods have been considered. With the assumption that the model switching is governed by an underlying Markov chain, the mixer uses the model probabilities and the model switching probabilities to compute a mixed estimate for each filter. At the beginning of a filtering cycle, each filter uses a mixed estimate and a measurement to compute a new estimate and a likelihood for the model within the filter. The likelihoods, prior model probabilities, and the model switching probabilities are then used to compute new model probabilities. The overall state estimate is then computed with the new state estimates and their model probabilities. The IMM algorithm is outlined in [1,3], while a derivation and detailed explanation of the IMM algorithm are given in [2,3].

4. Application of the IMM algorithm

The potential of the IMM algorithm for addressing the filter consistency problem illustrated in Section 2 will be assessed. The measurements of the two sensors

are corrupted with errors that are zero-mean Gaussian with a standard deviation of 25 m. Each sensor measures the target position at a 1 Hz rate with the measurement times of the two sensors being skewed by 0.5 s. The target maneuvers with a constant acceleration of 20 m/s² from 15 to 35 s. For the IMM algorithm, the models were chosen as (1) the constant velocity model with piecewise constant acceleration errors, and (2) constant acceleration model with piecewise constant acceleration errors. For the IMM algorithm, the process noise covariances were $Q_k^1 = 1.0 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^4$, and $Q_k^2 = 50.0 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^4$. The initial model probabilities were $\mu_0 = [0.75 \ 0.25]$ and the model switching probability matrix was chosen to be

$$\Pi = \begin{bmatrix} p_{11} & 1 - p_{11} \\ 1 - p_{22} & p_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

where $p_{11} = 1 - 0.1 T$ and $p_{22} = 1 - 0.15 T$.

Simulation results for the IMM algorithm are given in Fig. 4. The results are the average 200 experiments. The IMM algorithm provides significantly better tracking performance than the constant velocity filter considered in Section 2. Furthermore, the addition of the data from the second sensor provides reduced RMSEs in position and velocity throughout the trajectory.

5. Summary and conclusions

The problem of filter consistency in tracking maneuvering targets with multiple intermittent sensors has been illustrated and the use of the IMM algorithm for tracking has been demonstrated as a potential solution to the problem. However, the results of some case studies that involve two sensors with diverse measurement accuracies and data rates indicate that using the IMM algorithm does not fully solve the problem of filter consistency [1]. Considering the errors associated with the misalignment of the multiple sensors will further reduce the number of situations in which the tracking of maneuvering targets are improved through the fusion of redundant data from multiple sensors. On the other hand, when data association is a problem, integration of data from multiple sensors may provide significant advantages.

References

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Fig. 4. RMSE in the State Estimates for Example

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